

An Alternative Approach in Derivation of Dirac's Energy-Momentum Relation

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Abstract: This paper presents an innovative simple method to derive the relativistic energy-momentum relation which was developed by Nobel laureate Paul Dirac.

Keywords: Lorentz factor, relativistic momentum, special relativity, time dilation

1. Introduction

Einstein's special theory of relativity [1-4] revolutionized our understanding of space, time, and the fundamental relationship between mass and energy. In this connection, Paul Dirac developed a relativistic energy-momentum relation.

2. Derivation of the Relativistic Energy-Momentum Equation

In this section, the author of this article presents an innovative way to derive the Dirac's energy-momentum relation using Einstein's mass-energy equation $E = \gamma m_0 c^2$, relativistic momentum $P = \gamma m_0 v$, and the Lorentz factor γ [5-7].

$$\text{Here, } \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

$$E^2 = \gamma^2 m_0^2 c^4 = m_0^2 c^4 (\gamma^2 + 1 - 1) = m_0^2 c^4 \left(1 + \gamma^2 \frac{(\gamma^2 - 1)}{\gamma^2} \right)$$

$$\gamma^2 = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma^2} = 1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \Rightarrow \frac{v^2}{c^2} = 1 - \frac{1}{\gamma^2} \Rightarrow \frac{v^2}{c^2} = \frac{\gamma^2 - 1}{\gamma^2}$$

$$E^2 = m_0^2 c^4 \left(1 + \gamma^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) = m_0^2 c^4 + \gamma^2 m_0^2 v^2 c^2$$

$$E^2 = (m_0 c^2)^2 + (Pc)^2, \text{ which is the relativistic energy momentum relation.}$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, the relativistic energy-momentum relation has been derived in a straightforward manner. This new idea can enable the researchers for further involvements in the scientific research and development.

References

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